

Multi-objective Optimization of BERTopic for Large-scale Scholarly Literature Analysis: Application to Autoregressive Models

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Abstract

This study proposes a multi-objective optimization framework for BERTopic to advance large-scale scholarly literature analysis on autoregressive (AR) models, including ARIMA, TSAR, and hybrid machine learning approaches. Employing the Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II), we optimized the hyperparameters of UMAP and HDBSCAN with two objective functions—maximizing C_V coherence and Topic Diversity Score—under a feasibility constraint requiring at least 20 valid topics ($\approx 5\%$ of the corpus). In selecting optimal solutions, we further restricted the noise ratio (unassigned documents) to $\leq 30\%$ in order to suppress excessively noisy outputs. Applied to 25,077 academic articles published between 2020 and 2024, the optimized model achieved a C_V Coherence Score of 0.76, a Topic Diversity Score of 0.73, and identified 144 interpretable topics spanning domains such as environmental science, healthcare, and macroeconomic forecasting. Co-occurrence network analysis revealed that AR-based models are organized into two major clusters—environmental and ecological forecasting, and biomedical and signal-processing applications—with technological topics such as renewable energy, battery modeling, and vehicle control serving as interdisciplinary bridges. Complementary community analysis using UMAP-based clustering identified 13 semantically coherent communities, encompassing both large-scale themes (e.g., air pollution, energy markets) and smaller, domain-specific ones (e.g., traffic safety, financial inclusion, education and gender). These findings empirically demonstrate the extensive applicability of AR models across diverse scholarly domains, while also showing that the proposed optimization framework ensures enhanced interpretability and coverage in large-scale literature analysis characterized by thematic diversity. Beyond AR-based models, the framework holds promise as a robust approach for topic classification across a wide range of scholarly corpora.

1. Introduction

Autoregressive (AR) models represent a fundamental probabilistic framework for time series analysis and serve as the foundation for numerous statistical and machine learning approaches. Extended models such as ARIMA, the Triple Seasonal Autoregressive (TSAR) model, vector autoregression, and hybrid integrations have been widely applied in fields including economics, environmental science, energy forecasting, and healthcare. Their ability to capture temporal dependencies has made them indispensable in both theoretical and applied research.

In recent years, the scope and scale of AR-based model applications have expanded rapidly, accompanied by a sustained increase in scholarly publications. This proliferation of research presents the challenge of systematically mapping, interpreting, and synthesizing trends across a large and diverse body of literature. To address this challenge, topic modeling offers a promising approach for extracting thematic structures and identifying cross-domain relationships. However, the quality and interpretability of topic models—particularly transformer-based methods such as BERTopic—are highly sensitive to hyperparameter choices in dimensionality reduction and clustering. Without systematic optimization—especially through multi-objective

approaches such as evolutionary algorithms—these models risk producing incoherent topics, redundant clusters, or an excessive number of unassigned documents.

In this study, we develop a multi-objective optimization framework for BERTopic based on NSGA-II, designed to optimize two objectives—C_V coherence and topic diversity—while imposing a feasibility constraint that requires at least 20 valid topics ($\approx 5\%$ of the corpus). To further promote interpretable solutions, we introduce a post-selection threshold limiting the noise ratio (the proportion of unassigned documents) to $\leq 30\%$. Applied to a large-scale corpus of 25,077 academic articles on AR-based models published between 2020 and 2024, the framework achieves balanced trade-offs between interpretability and coverage, thereby improving topic quality and thematic mapping.

The main contributions of this work are:

1. A multi-objective optimization approach for BERTopic that targets coherence and diversity as two objectives, with a minimum topic-count feasibility constraint (≥ 20 , $\approx 1\%$), plus a post-selection noise threshold ($\leq 30\%$) to enhance interpretability.
2. A large-scale empirical analysis of AR-based literature from 2020–2024, revealing key thematic areas and cross-domain links.
3. A multi-objective optimization framework with a clearly defined design process and evaluation methodology, demonstrating applicability to other large-scale scholarly corpora.

2. Related Work

BERTopic has emerged as a prominent embedding-based topic modeling method for extracting latent thematic structures from academic literature, complementing traditional probabilistic and matrix factorization approaches. Classical models such as Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), Hierarchical Dirichlet Process (HDP), and Dynamic Topic Modeling (DTM) have been widely used, alongside Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) and more recent embedding-based approaches such as Top2Vec. BERTopic leverages transformer-based language models, notably BERT (Devlin et al., 2019), to generate document embeddings, followed by dimensionality reduction and density-based clustering.

Several studies have compared BERTopic to conventional techniques. Egger and Yu (2022) found that both BERTopic and NMF achieved high classification accuracy in social media analysis. Pavithra and Savitha (2024), in a comparative study involving LDA, HDP, NMF, BERTopic, and DTM for academic literature, concluded that DTM provided the most effective results, with the others—BERTopic included—showing broadly comparable performance. Other applications of BERTopic in scholarly contexts include He et al. (2025) and Al Azher et al. (2025), which demonstrated its capacity to uncover domain-specific topic structures.

Despite these strengths, the interpretability of BERTopic classifications is highly dependent on the hyperparameter settings in its dimensionality reduction (UMAP) and clustering (HDBSCAN) stages. Farea et al. (2024) reported that both LDA and BERTopic have a tendency to overestimate the number of topics, thereby reducing interpretability. Grootendorst, the principal developer of BERTopic, emphasizes that parameters such as `n_neighbors` and `min_dist` in UMAP, and `min_cluster_size` and `min_samples` in HDBSCAN, can substantially affect topic coherence and cluster quality. Similarly, Medveckı et al. (2024) have underscored the importance of careful hyperparameter tuning for stable classification, especially in multilingual settings.

While these studies evaluated BERTopic in comparative settings, few have systematically addressed the challenge of multi-objective hyperparameter tuning. Addressing this gap, the present study introduces and evaluates a multi-objective optimization framework specifically tailored to enhance BERTopic’s performance in large-scale scholarly literature analysis.

3. Method

3.1 Data collection

The dataset employed in this study was obtained from Elsevier’s Scopus database via the Scopus API. Publications were included if the term “Autoregressive” or its variants (“AR Model,” “Autoregressive Model,” or “auto-regressive”) appeared in the title, abstract, or keywords (TITLE-ABS-KEY). The search period spanned from January 1, 2020, to December 31, 2024. To restrict the scope to original research outputs, the document type (DOCTYPE) was limited to “Articles,” thereby excluding conference papers, reviews, and other formats from the analysis. To ensure comprehensive retrieval, the API was queried iteratively by publication year. Each record was uniquely identified using its Scopus ID, and duplicates were eliminated. The dataset contained metadata fields including article title, DOI, authors, journal name, citation count, publication year, subject area, and abstract.

In total, 25,077 articles were collected: 3,870 in 2020, 4,471 in 2021, 5,156 in 2022, 5,372 in 2023, and 6,208 in 2024. This corpus served as the input for the topic modeling analysis described in the following section.

3.2 Proposed Multi-objective Optimization Framework for BERTopic

In recent years, document analysis models employing BERTopic have attracted considerable attention as applied methodologies for uncovering latent thematic structures in academic literature, such as in systematic reviews. In the present study, BERTopic was likewise adopted to extract topics from a large-scale corpus of scholarly articles. BERTopic is a machine learning–based topic modeling approach that transforms documents into semantic sentence embeddings and identifies topics based on their distributional similarity.

For sentence embedding, we employed the Sentence-BERT model (*all-mpnet-base-v2*), which generates 768-dimensional dense vector representations. Dimensionality reduction was carried out using the UMAP (Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection) algorithm with cosine distance, and clustering was performed via HDBSCAN (Hierarchical Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise).

Although alternative topic modeling approaches—such as Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF), Top2Vec, and Dynamic Topic Modeling (DTM)—have been extensively studied, prior research (e.g., Egger & Yu, 2022; Pavithra & Savitha, 2024) has reported that BERTopic, based on the BERT architecture (Devlin et al., 2019), demonstrates competitive or superior classification accuracy across diverse contexts. Nevertheless, as emphasized by Farea et al. (2024), Medveckı et al. (2024), and the system’s developer Grootendorst (2024), hyperparameter tuning—particularly within UMAP and HDBSCAN—exerts a substantial influence on topic coherence, stability, and interpretability.

To address this issue, we formulated the selection of BERTopic hyperparameters as a bi-objective constrained optimization problem. The search space encompassed $n_neighbors$, min_dist , and $n_components$ for UMAP; $min_cluster_size$ and $min_samples$ for HDBSCAN; and top_n_words and min_topic_size for BERTopic itself. The optimization objectives were defined as follows:

- Maximization of C_V Coherence: quantifying the semantic consistency of top-ranked words within each topic.
- Maximization of Topic Diversity: defined as the proportion of unique lexical items relative to the total lexical items across all topics.

A single feasibility constraint was imposed requiring the number of valid topics to be no fewer than $MIN_TOPICS = 20$. Given the corpus size of approximately 25,000 documents, this threshold ensured that, on average, each topic comprised about 1,200 documents ($\approx 5\%$ of the

corpus). The lower bound was introduced to prevent overly coarse-grained solutions, thereby maintaining adequate thematic diversity while preserving interpretability.

Following the multi-objective optimization, we conducted a systematic post hoc analysis of all candidate solutions. For each trial, parameter configurations, C_V coherence scores, diversity scores, noise ratios, and topic counts were recorded, and the complete trial history was preserved in tabular form to ensure reproducibility.

To guarantee practical feasibility, candidate solutions were filtered according to the following three criteria:

- (i) C_V score ≥ 0.5
- (ii) Number of topics ≥ 20 ($\approx 5\%$ of the corpus)
- (iii) Compliance with the feasibility constraint

Solutions that satisfied these conditions underwent a two-stage evaluation. First, coherence and diversity scores were normalized using min-max scaling, and a combined score was computed as the weighted sum of the two metrics:

$$\text{Combined Score} = 0.5 \times \text{C_V coherence} + 0.5 \times \text{Topic diversity}$$

Based on this combined score, the top 20 solutions were retained as Pareto candidate reports.

Second, an additional constraint was introduced to regulate noise levels. Solutions with a noise ratio $\leq 30\%$ were re-normalized and re-scored within this subset, producing a refined ranking of candidate solutions. Among these, the solution with the highest combined score was designated as the optimal solution.

4. Analysis Results

The optimal parameter configuration derived from the above multi-objective optimization process achieved a C_V Coherence Score of 0.76 and a Topic Diversity Score of 0.73, yielding 144 interpretable topics, while the noise ratio was constrained to 28.56%. A summary of the topic frequency distribution is presented in Figure 1, and representative keywords for the most frequent topics are provided in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Number of Topics and Cumulative Distribution.

Figure 2. Summary of the Top-ranked Topics over 1% proportion.

Topic	Count	Proportion	Representation	Topic	Count	Proportion	Representation
Topic 0	3,420	19.09%	energy, environmental, emission, renewable, consumption	Topic 81	52	0.29%	bitcoin, cryptocurrency, price, cryptocurrencies, learning
Topic 1	822	4.59%	symptom, longitudinal, crosslagged, depression, depressive	Topic 82	52	0.29%	suicide, selfharm, mental, pandemic, search
Topic 2	805	4.49%	water, rainfall, river, precipitation, drought	Topic 83	50	0.28%	light, curve, optical, apo, variability
Topic 3	769	4.29%	oil, price, market, crude, shock	Topic 84	49	0.27%	network, topology, node, graphical, graph
Topic 4	409	2.28%	tourism, tourist, arrival, demand, growth	Topic 85	48	0.27%	housing, spatial, urban, retail, property
Topic 5	381	2.13%	load, electricity, forecasting, energy, building	Topic 86	48	0.27%	ar, reality, 3d, augmented, anatomy
Topic 6	368	2.05%	volatility, realized, garch, stock, return	Topic 87	47	0.26%	ship, control, motion, heave
Topic 7	359	2.00%	covid19, case, arima, confirmed, spread	Topic 88	47	0.26%	road, accident, traffic, crash, safety
Topic 8	314	1.75%	fiscal, debt, deficit, public, tax	Topic 89	46	0.26%	crash, safety, road, traffic, pedestrian
Topic 9	283	1.58%	integervalued, count, poisson, process, binomial	Topic 90	43	0.24%	ionospheric, tec, electron, geomagnetic, solar
Topic 10	280	1.56%	traffic, flow, passenger, prediction, travel	Topic 91	43	0.24%	modal, identification, bridge, mode, frequency
Topic 11	268	1.50%	air, concentration, pollution, pminf25inf, quality	Topic 92	41	0.23%	corruption, economic, egovernment, nigeria, growth
Topic 12	266	1.48%	spatial, estimator, estimation, selection, sar	Topic 93	41	0.23%	control, controller, predictive, process
Topic 13	250	1.40%	bitcoin, cryptocurrencies, cryptocurrency, market, volatility	Topic 94	41	0.23%	antibiotic, antimicrobial, infection, resistance, prescribing
Topic 14	236	1.32%	identification, algorithm, parameter, noise	Topic 95	40	0.22%	reservoir, computing, rc, task, photonic
Topic 15	227	1.27%	wind, speed, power, forecasting, prediction	Topic 96	40	0.22%	process, monitoring, fault, dynamic, detection
Topic 16	201	1.12%	crime, alcohol, firearm, cannabis, violence	Topic 97	39	0.22%	heart, hrv, variability, autonomic, cardiovascular
Topic 17	196	1.09%	language, text, translation, generation, transformer	Topic 98	39	0.22%	emission, carbon, grey, peak, conf2inf
Topic 18	184	1.03%	solar, pv, irradiance, photovoltaic, power	Topic 99	39	0.22%	military, spending, defence, expenditure, nato
Topic 19	175	0.98%	housing, house, estate, price, real	Topic 100	39	0.22%	workload, cloud, resource, computing, vm
Topic 20	174	0.97%	price, production, forecasting, arima, milk	Topic 101	38	0.21%	specie, richness, diversity, bird, phylogenetic
Topic 21	163	0.91%	fdi, foreign, investment, direct, inflow	Topic 102	38	0.21%	power, energy, scheduling, generation
Topic 22	161	0.90%	stock, forecasting, price, arima, market	Topic 103	38	0.21%	teaching, education, topic, student, academic
Topic 23	154	0.86%	incidence, hfmd, hfns, sarima, brucellosis	Topic 104	38	0.21%	money, monetary, demand, inflation, supply
Topic 24	152	0.85%	image, compression, video, motion, generative	Topic 105	36	0.20%	production, shale, reservoir, gas
Topic 25	146	0.82%	fault, bearing, diagnosis, signal, vibration	Topic 106	36	0.20%	speech, signal, vocal, tract, glottal
Topic 26	143	0.80%	price, food, market, pork, transmission	Topic 107	36	0.20%	clock, satellite, positioning, ambiguity, ppp
Topic 27	140	0.78%	monetary, policy, shock, uncertainty, unconventional	Topic 108	35	0.20%	temperature, weather, lstm, prediction, deep
Topic 28	139	0.78%	financial, inclusion, development, growth, economic	Topic 109	35	0.20%	navigation, gyroscope, gnss, mem, kalman
Topic 29	136	0.76%	battery, lithiumion, soc, soh, estimation	Topic 110	35	0.20%	bayesian, tsar, prior, posterior, distribution
Topic 30	134	0.75%	damage, structural, structure, identification, detection	Topic 111	35	0.20%	pest, hive, fruit, germanica, hopper
Topic 31	133	0.74%	exchange, rate, trade, balance, export	Topic 112	35	0.20%	glucose, mgdl, blood, diabetes, hypoglycemia
Topic 32	114	0.64%	demand, chain, inventory, supply, forecasting	Topic 113	35	0.20%	furnace, boiler, blast, combustion, gas
Topic 33	112	0.63%	nasal, ar, allergic, rhinitis, cell	Topic 114	34	0.19%	structural, identification, vector, shock, nongaussian
Topic 34	106	0.59%	connectivity, brain, fMRI, functional, network	Topic 115	34	0.19%	markov, chain, ergodic, process, theorem
Topic 35	101	0.56%	bank, islamic, banking, deposit, loan	Topic 116	33	0.18%	flutter, aerodynamic, aeroelastic, rom, reducedorder
Topic 36	98	0.55%	unemployment, cpi, forecasting, forecast, gdp	Topic 117	33	0.18%	estimator, panel, moment, biascorrected, gmm
Topic 37	97	0.54%	volatility, spillover, market, stock, contagion	Topic 118	33	0.18%	trip, transit, bike, bikesharing, bikeshare
Topic 38	97	0.54%	chart, control, arl, ewma, autocorrelated	Topic 119	33	0.18%	political, social, medium, protest, news
Topic 39	97	0.54%	stock, covid19, market, pandemic, volatility	Topic 120	33	0.18%	marketing, brand, sale, online, medium
Topic 40	97	0.54%	eeg, classification, feature, seizure, brain	Topic 121	32	0.18%	asymptotic, estimator, process, random, deviation
Topic 41	96	0.54%	sea, ice, climate, forcing, variability	Topic 122	32	0.18%	waste, msw, generation, municipal, solid
Topic 42	95	0.53%	dengue, incidence, malaria, case, disease	Topic 123	31	0.17%	uncertain, imprecise, estimation, unknown
Topic 43	94	0.52%	oil, volatility, crude, realized, outofsample	Topic 124	30	0.17%	texture, classification, feature, image, cancer
Topic 44	89	0.50%	abundance, specie, fish, fishery, spatiotemporal	Topic 125	30	0.17%	container, throughput, port, freight, forecasting
Topic 45	87	0.49%	landslide, displacement, deformation, prediction, dam	Topic 126	29	0.16%	construction, cost, project, labor, material
Topic 46	86	0.48%	remittance, inflow, remittances, worker, poverty	Topic 127	29	0.16%	polar, earth, lod, eop, prediction
Topic 47	85	0.47%	hysteresis, actuator, controller, control, piezoelectric	Topic 128	28	0.16%	wastewater, effluent, treatment, plant, ph
Topic 48	85	0.47%	stock, market, exchange, rate, macroeconomic	Topic 129	28	0.16%	volatility, lstm, garch, garlic, memory
Topic 49	85	0.47%	emg, semg, gait, limb, muscle	Topic 130	28	0.16%	break, point, change, structural, asymptotic
Topic 50	81	0.45%	opioid, prescription, drug, prescribing, pandemic	Topic 131	26	0.15%	sovereign, cd, swap, default, bond
Topic 51	80	0.45%	spatial, regional, region, spillover, innovation	Topic 132	25	0.14%	population, abundance, harvest, specie, deer
Topic 52	80	0.45%	education, labour, female, participation, human	Topic 133	25	0.14%	distribution, likelihood, normal, maximum, estimation
Topic 53	79	0.44%	ecg, signal, heart, arrhythmia, classification	Topic 134	25	0.14%	inequality, income, growth, economic, globalisation
Topic 54	77	0.43%	channel, fading, communication, mimo, csi	Topic 135	25	0.14%	pandemic, covid19, excess, hospitalization, mortality
Topic 55	76	0.42%	price, crude, oil, forecasting, carbon	Topic 136	24	0.13%	vehicle, braking, control, driving, steering
Topic 56	75	0.42%	radar, target, clutter, detection, interference	Topic 137	24	0.13%	fertility, mortality, birth, pregnancy, maternal
Topic 57	75	0.42%	spatial, covid19, mortality, accessibility, death	Topic 138	23	0.13%	pemfc, cell, fuel, membrane, proton
Topic 58	74	0.41%	test, asymptotic, unit, root, statistic	Topic 139	23	0.13%	stunting, child, malnutrition, spatial, undernutrition
Topic 59	72	0.40%	air, pollution, noinf2inf, covid19, admission	Topic 140	22	0.12%	wave, ocean, height, prediction, predication
Topic 60	71	0.40%	spatial, disease, cancer, bayesian, mapping	Topic 141	22	0.12%	mortality, leecarter, expectancy, life, lc
Topic 61	70	0.39%	quantile, conditional, asymptotic, estimator, test	Topic 142	22	0.12%	wind, tower, vibration, windinduced, crane
Topic 62	65	0.36%	speech, synthesis, speaker, endtoend, nonautoregressive	Topic 143	22	0.12%	sentiment, news, index, shipping, stock
Topic 63	65	0.36%	ict, innovation, rd, patent, growth				
Topic 64	64	0.36%	agricultural, agriculture, credit, productivity, sector				
Topic 65	64	0.36%	vegetation, forest, wildfire, climate				
Topic 66	63	0.35%	molecular, molecule, protein, design, generative				
Topic 67	60	0.33%	anomaly, detection, network, attack, ddos				
Topic 68	60	0.33%	tuberculosis, tb, incidence, ptb, pulmonary				
Topic 69	59	0.33%	inertia, power, controller, wind				
Topic 70	59	0.33%	blood, hospital, emergency, cd, patient				
Topic 71	57	0.32%	machining, deformation, thermal, cutting, force				
Topic 72	56	0.31%	stem, tree, taper, diameter, volume				
Topic 73	56	0.31%	health, expenditure, mortality, healthcare, income				
Topic 74	55	0.31%	series, hybrid, time, forecasting, hybridization				
Topic 75	55	0.31%	quantum, spin, neural, manybody, variational				
Topic 76	55	0.31%	burden, 2019, disease, mortality, rate				
Topic 77	53	0.30%	traffic, network, prediction, mobile, sdn				
Topic 78	53	0.30%	earthquake, seismic, picking, anomaly, noise				
Topic 79	52	0.29%	cancer, burden, incidence, mortality, breast				
Topic 80	52	0.29%	trade, openness, growth, economic, export				

Among the 144 interpretable topics, the top 13 topics accounted for 50.21% of all classified documents. Notably, Topic 0 represented 19.09% of the corpus, indicating a marked concentration in certain thematic areas. The overall topic frequency distribution follows a Zipf-like pattern, with a small number of high-frequency topics dominating and a long tail of lower-frequency topics.

The list of topics identified from the retrieved corpus is presented in Figure 2, with noise topics excluded. An overview of the distribution reveals that the largest topic, accounting for approximately 19% of the corpus, pertains to Energy, Environment, and Renewable Resources (Topic 0), reflecting a pronounced concentration on issues related to climate change and sustainability. In contrast, topics associated with Psychiatric Research (Topic 1), Water Resource Management (Topic 2), and Oil Markets (Topic 3) each comprised around 4% of the corpus, suggesting that AR models have been substantially employed in research domains with significant societal impact. Furthermore, several smaller topics, each representing approximately 1–2% of the corpus, were identified, including Tourism (Topic 4), Electricity Demand Forecasting (Topic 5), Financial Market Volatility (Topic 6), COVID-19 (Topic 7), Fiscal Policy (Topic 8), Traffic Flow (Topic 10), Air Pollution (Topic 11), Cryptocurrency (Topic 13), and Natural Language Processing (Topic 17).

Taken together, these findings demonstrate that AR-based modeling is predominantly concentrated in Energy and Environment (Topic 0), while simultaneously extending across a wide range of disciplines, including Medicine (Topic 1), Economics (Topics 3, 6, 8, 13), Social Sciences (Topics 10, 16), Engineering (Topics 5, 15, 18), and Information Science (Topics 12, 14, 17). This attests to both the diversity and interdisciplinary applicability of AR models, which have been successfully captured through the proposed multi-objective optimization framework.

To examine the structural relationships among topics derived from AR-based literature, we first constructed a topic co-occurrence network based on topic probability distributions (Figure 3). Topics were selected as follows: for each paper, topics with a topic probability of at least 0.012 were included—the threshold was empirically determined to balance the inclusion of meaningful topic associations with the need for network stability and interpretability—and only papers containing 30 or more such topics were retained. Within these papers, all topic pairs were counted as co-occurrence candidates. Co-occurrence strengths were normalized using pointwise mutual information (PMI), and only pairs with sufficiently high PMI values were retained as edges. Isolated nodes were removed, betweenness centrality was used to evaluate the relative influence of topics, and the Kamada–Kawai layout was employed for visualization. Nodes with yellow–green shades represent topics with higher centrality scores.

The resulting AR-based topic network revealed two major clusters. The first cluster (e.g., Topics 11, 41, 44, 72, 101, 132) centers on environmental and ecological applications of AR models, including studies on air pollution forecasting, sea-ice variability, biodiversity and species abundance, forestry, and fisheries. These areas highlight how AR-based approaches are used to capture complex environmental and climatic dynamics. The second cluster (e.g., Topics 10, 17, 34, 40, 53, 62, 106, 112, 124) is dominated by biomedical and signal-processing applications, encompassing traffic flow prediction, natural language and speech modeling, EEG/ECG time-series analysis, functional brain networks, diabetes monitoring, and medical image classification. This indicates the broad adoption of AR-based models in life sciences and health-related signal analysis.

Bridging these two clusters are technological topics such as Topic 18 (solar photovoltaic power modeling), Topic 29 (lithium-ion battery degradation and state-of-charge estimation), and Topic 136 (vehicle braking and control). Their high betweenness centrality suggests that energy technologies, storage systems, and vehicular dynamics research function as interdisciplinary connectors. These bridging topics are particularly notable because AR-based frameworks provide tools for forecasting, anomaly detection, and control across both environmental and biomedical domains. Conversely, certain topics such as Topic 138 (proton-exchange membrane

fuel cells) remain peripheral, reflecting niche AR-based applications with limited connectivity.

Taken together, the analysis demonstrates that AR-based modeling research is organized into two principal clusters—environmental/ecological forecasting and biomedical/signal-processing applications—while technological domains such as renewable energy, batteries, and vehicle control act as bridges between them. These bridging topics may represent key interdisciplinary loci where methodological advances in AR-based modeling contribute simultaneously to sustainability research and biomedical innovation.

Figure 3. Topic Co-occurrence Network diagram.

The two-cluster structure revealed by the co-occurrence analysis provides a coarse-grained view of topic relationships. To obtain a more fine-grained understanding, we further decomposed this structure into multiple semantically coherent communities using a UMAP-based embedding and clustering approach.

Building upon the co-occurrence analysis, Figure 4 visualizes the semantic relationships among topics by applying a two-dimensional UMAP projection combined with community detection. This approach enables the identification of 13 distinct communities (C0–C12), each representing semantically coherent subfields. Figure 5 summarizes the communities with topic counts and representative labels. In this visualization, the size of each node corresponds to the

number of documents assigned to the topic, while clusters are delineated through community detection applied to topic embeddings. The analysis identified thirteen semantically coherent communities (see also Figure 2 for details on topic counts and representative labels).

The largest community (C0, 13 topics) is associated with *air*, *concentration*, and *pollution*, centering on research related to air quality and atmospheric studies. Community C1 (7 topics) is organized around *oil*, *price*, and *market*, focusing on energy markets and commodity price dynamics. Community C2 (6 topics), characterized by *covid19*, *case*, and *arima*, reflects research on epidemiological modeling and pandemic-related forecasting. Other medium-sized clusters include C3 (4 topics: *volatility*, *spillover*, *market*), which addresses financial risk transmission, and C4 (3 topics: *load*, *electricity*, *forecasting*), which emphasizes energy demand prediction.

In addition, several small, highly specialized clusters composed of two topics each are observed. These include *financial inclusion and development* (C5), *spatial covid19 mortality* (C6), *traffic flow and passenger dynamics* (C7), *foreign direct investment* (C8), *road accidents and traffic safety* (C9), *structural damage* (C10), *monetary policy shocks* (C11), and *education, labour, and gender* (C12).

Examining the spatial configuration of the identified communities reveals that medical-related clusters (C2 and C6) are located at a distance from the other groups, while C0, which encompasses a broad range of topics, is positioned in an intermediate location. This spatial arrangement suggests semantic linkages involving AR-based time series modeling. Furthermore, the coexistence of large thematic clusters alongside small, domain-specific ones indicates that the optimized BERTopic model effectively captures both broad research trends and niche areas of inquiry, thereby reflecting the semantic diversity of the corpus.

Figure 4. Intertopic Map of Communities Based on UMAP Projection.

Figure 5. Summary of Topic Communities with Counts and Representative Labels

Community	Topic count	Label
C0	13	air, concentration, pollution
C1	7	oil, price, market
C2	6	covid19, case, arima
C3	4	volatility, spillover, market
C4	3	load, electricity, forecasting
C5	2	financial, inclusion, development
C6	2	spatial, covid19, mortality
C7	2	traffic, flow, passenger
C8	2	fdi, foreign, investment
C9	2	road, accident, traffic
C10	2	damage, structural, structure
C11	2	monetary, policy, shock
C12	2	education, labour, female

5. Conclusion

This study experimentally developed and applied a multi-objective optimization framework for BERTopic to analyze large-scale scholarly literature on autoregressive (AR)-based models. The framework, which jointly optimized the C_V Coherence Score and Topic Diversity Score under a practical constraint on topic count, enabled an objective and reproducible topic modeling process. While the trade-off between coherence and diversity remains inherent to topic modeling, the results demonstrated that balanced and interpretable topic classifications can be achieved through systematic tuning strategies.

The large-scale analysis of 25,077 scholarly articles revealed the extensive applicability of AR-based models across diverse research domains. Prominent applications were observed in environmental sciences (e.g., precipitation modeling, CO₂ emissions analysis), medical and psychological research (e.g., depression studies, EEG and fMRI analysis), and economic and financial forecasting (e.g., cryptocurrency markets, crude oil price prediction, GDP estimation). The breadth of topics identified underscores the versatility of AR-based approaches in both theoretical and applied contexts.

To elucidate the structural relationships among these topics, a co-occurrence network analysis was first conducted. This revealed a two-cluster structure, broadly separating environmental/ecological research from biomedical and signal-processing applications, while highlighting bridging roles played by technological domains such as renewable energy, battery modeling, and vehicle control. Building upon this analysis, a community detection approach based on UMAP embedding further decomposed the topic space into 13 semantically coherent communities. The co-occurrence analysis thus emphasized bridging and central topics, whereas the community analysis provided a finer-grained thematic organization of the corpus. Together, these complementary methods revealed that AR-based models serve as a foundational analytical framework that connects otherwise disparate research fields.

These findings suggest that AR-based modeling not only supports methodological integration but also fosters interdisciplinary knowledge exchange. By bridging environmental sustainability, biomedical innovation, and economic forecasting, AR-based models demonstrate their unique role as a versatile and unifying approach in contemporary data-driven science. At the same time, by successfully ensuring interpretability in the document analysis of AR models—which themselves provide a broad and cross-disciplinary analytical approach—the proposed framework is expected to secure objectivity and feasibility in other forms of literature analysis as well, through systematic hyperparameter tuning. In this sense, the contribution of the framework should be regarded as far from insignificant.

6. Limitations and Future Work

While this study adopted BERTopic as the primary topic modeling approach, the optimization process relied on a limited set of evaluation metrics—namely, the C_V Coherence Score, Topic Diversity Score, and a constraint on topic count. Although these metrics enabled a balanced trade-off between interpretability and diversity, numerous alternative criteria, such as topic stability, perplexity, or human-centered interpretability ratings, could also be incorporated to establish a more comprehensive basis for hyperparameter optimization. Expanding the range of evaluation criteria would allow for a richer and more nuanced assessment of model performance across different dimensions of quality.

Another limitation concerns the relationship between evaluation metrics and the determination of the appropriate number of topics relative to corpus size. Both factors can substantially influence interpretability, thematic granularity, and the ability to capture meaningful structures within the literature. For example, the identification of two large-scale clusters in the co-occurrence network and the subsequent decomposition into 13 communities using UMAP-based clustering underscores how parameter settings shape the granularity of the resulting topic space. Systematic exploration of these parameter choices—potentially through sensitivity analyses—would improve the generalizability and robustness of the proposed framework.

Future research should extend the evaluation of topic stability and robustness by implementing cross-validation techniques. Moreover, expert-based validation processes—where domain specialists assess the conceptual coherence, domain relevance, and practical applicability of extracted topics—would provide valuable qualitative verification to complement quantitative metrics. In addition, integrating network-based measures (e.g., centrality or modularity from co-occurrence networks) with community-level evaluations could yield more holistic criteria for assessing topic quality. Such integrative evaluation strategies would enhance both the methodological rigor and applied value of multi-objective optimization frameworks for large-scale scholarly literature analysis.

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